

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH SPORTS

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Annotation: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of national identity in students through sports, the role of national traditional values of holidays, ceremonies, customs and events as a source of national education are of particular importance. playing was explained.

Key words and phrases: sports, folk traditional values, intercultural relations, practical skills, continuous education, individual qualities, economic development, educational standards, education and training, scientific-methodical, subjective innovation in students.

Introduction

Forming a healthy lifestyle in our society, creating conditions suitable for students to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, strengthening confidence in one's own will, strength and ability, courage and patriotism, In order to develop feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, to further develop physical education and mass sports, to attract all layers of the population, especially young people, to regularly engage in physical education and sports, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 "Physical Decision No. PQ-3031 on measures for the further development of education and public sports is being adopted. According to him, "scientific-methodical support of training, retraining and professional development institutions in the field of physical education and sports, as well as providing sports schools with highly qualified trainers and medical personnel, their education "Today's era itself shows the importance of defining functional tasks in educational institutions".[1] In fact, one of the important tasks in the formation of physical culture among students is the training of modern personnel in the field of physical education and sports, improving their qualifications, and creating ample opportunities for teachers-coaches.

All subjects of primary education are taught on the basis of curricula, including physical education. Physical education of students, their physical development and health is the main issue in all the work carried out in connection with the improvement of primary education.

At this point, we considered it permissible to pay special attention to the physical education of primary school students. Physical education of primary school students today:

- physical education classes;
- extracurricular activities;
- physical education work in non-school institutions;
- it is carried out in the form of family physical education classes.

In 2017, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the subject of physical education in the State Education Standard and the curriculum of general education schools. - 66 hours for classes, 68 hours for classes 2-3-4, as well as training of sports such as gymnastics, athletics, action games, elements of sports games: basketball, volleyball, handball, football, chess

According to the content and organization of the physical education lesson, it has its own characteristics and is held in a sports hall, special facilities, playgrounds, school yard, stadium corridors, special conditions are created for students in such places. . Pupils are required to wear special sports clothes instead of regular school uniforms in physical education classes. It will be convenient to perform physical activities.

In order to make pedagogical activities aimed at forming physical culture in students more effective in the general secondary education system, the following tasks should be performed:

- regular monitoring of the growth of students' mental abilities, as well as the improvement of their physical qualities;
- to determine the achievements and shortcomings in the formation of physical culture of students during the educational process and to determine the relevant tasks based on this;
- based on the experience of developed countries, improving the system of preparing students for mass sports rehabilitation;
- development of the most optimal system of training specialists for the preparation of students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation and its effective use in practice;
- further strengthening of scientific research in this direction is considered very important.

It became known that some physical education classes were not held at the required level and there were serious deficiencies in the physical education classes taught. These include:

- the attitude of most school management towards physical education classes is not positive. (He does not consider physical education lessons as an important lesson).

- low potential of teachers, their failure to work on themselves or failure to follow existing rules.

- lack of equipment for organizing and conducting physical education classes.

- the absence of a perfect textbook on physical education for primary classes.

- lack of special facilities for organizing and conducting physical education classes.

- insufficient organization and discussion of open physical education lessons.

In order to eliminate the above deficiencies, we believe that it is necessary to implement the following works and give them as a recommendation.

- achieving accurate and correct planning of physical education lessons (annual, quarterly, monthly and weekly);

- to ensure the availability of facilities and equipment necessary for physical education classes;

- adhere to the conduct of the physical education lesson in accordance with other subjects of the educational agenda;

- taking into account the need to implement other types of education in physical education classes;

- it is necessary to develop a mechanism to increase the motivation of the physical education teacher for professional activity;

- it is necessary to supervise the management of the organization and conduct of physical education classes based on the State Education Standard.

- to organize and conduct physical education classes based on national and universal values. The main tasks of physical education to educate students through sports and guide them to a healthy lifestyle, exercise, physical development, movement skills and abilities are as follows:

1. Strengthening health, helping students to develop and train properly.

"Under the influence of natural factors, water, sun, and air, the health of students can be strengthened, trained, and the body's resistance to diseases increased. Carrying out physical education classes in fresh air as much as possible or organizing sports halls with fresh air. Lead students in water treatments, swimming and bathing, and sunbathing activities. These activities are carried out during walks, excursions and tourism activities. This task is the most important of all physical culture and sports activities in the school. It should be the center of attention of every teacher and team of pedagogues. School age is a

period of rapid growth and physical development of children. Therefore, it is necessary to spend as much effort as possible for the normal physical development of schoolchildren. Height is of particular importance in the harmonious development of students. The correct development and normal functioning of all internal organs is related to height".[7] Therefore, natural factors of nature are widely used to strengthen health and train the body.

2. Providing special knowledge about physical education and sports in the education of students by means of sports, healthy, guiding them to a healthy lifestyle, instilling in them hygienic knowledge and skills. This task is to provide students with the necessary knowledge about the benefits of physical training, hygiene rules, as well as "the rules of correct performance of all physical exercises provided for in the program. All of these are directly related to the strengthening of children's health, their knowledge of hygiene rules and their adherence to them, and this is achieved by the joint action of the school, family, community, and children themselves. Exercise and sports are taught in physical education classes, daily activities and club activities. As a result, children's physical development is ensured".[8] Also, students are interested in sports and are attracted to sports.

3. Formation and improvement of movement skills and abilities, training in new movement types and movement activities. The content of the school's physical education program is structured in such a way that students regularly practice in physical education classes, at home, in physical education clubs and sports clubs, and systematically acquire vital movement skills such as walking, running, throwing, scrambling, and balancing, will take over. All of the listed activities will help children develop in all aspects of physical development and prepare them for work. It is necessary to approach students according to their gender, age and physical fitness as well as their personal abilities in the formation of movement skills and abilities.

4. Development of physical qualities and abilities in education of students through sports. Speed, strength, agility and endurance and flexibility are qualities that everyone needs. They are closely related to the formation of movement skills in children. Carrying out physical exercises for a short or long time at different speeds and with different complications helps to develop the above qualities.

5. Educating moral and aesthetic qualities in educating students through sports. Cultivation of bravery, determination, discipline, sense of community, friendship and camaraderie, cultural behavior skills, attitude to work and social

property. The whole process of physical education helps to cultivate such valuable moral and willful qualities. Many physical exercises and play activities help to develop chivalry and friendship. Also, formation and upbringing of children's love for the Motherland, patriotism, feelings.

6. Involvement of students based on new approaches to physical education and sports training in sports education. The task of physical education at school is to accustom children to systematic physical exercises not only at school, but also at home. In order to fulfill this important task, all activities with children should be lively, the content and form of the learning material should be interesting, under the sincere treatment of the instructor, and the conditions for the participants to cooperate in a friendly manner. need to create. Encouraging students to engage in sports according to their personal interests and physical abilities. Also, general physical training and sports training for residential areas, schools, and sports clubs.

The tasks given in the course of physical education are performed in the form of certain physical exercises. In addition to giving exercises to perform, the teacher should explain to the students not what to do and how to do it, but also the fact that it is recommended to do this exercise and that this rule should be followed.

Exercise is voluntary action controlled by the mind. In the formation of movement skills, the performance of movements is raised to the level of automation. It cannot be said that there is no conscious movement, because one consciously learns physical exercises in order to bring the movement to the level of automation. Teachers and trainers monitor, evaluate and correct the mistakes of the participants. Nevertheless, it is important to develop the ability of the participants to evaluate and control their own actions. In this, the methods of pre-sensing and testing actions are often used.

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